

The Relationship of Bacteria and Biofilm Formation in Infected Patients. The Case of Iraq, Al-Rifai Teaching Hospital

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Abstract

Biofilms, a bacterial survival strategy, can grow at the primary focus of infection and allow bacteria to spread via the bloodstream. Biofilms can hematogenously disseminate both planktonic bacteria and biofilm fragments, a case-control study including 250 samples suspected of bacterial biofilm infections were collected from Al-Rifai General Hospital, Thi-Qar city, Southern Iraq, between December 2025 and April 2026 from patients aged between 10 and 45 years. The current results showed that 100 (40.0%) samples were positive and 150 (60.0%) samples were negative for bacterial biofilm formation. These results show that the prevalence of bacterial biofilm is higher in Gram-negative bacteria compared to Gram-positive bacteria (66 (66.0%) vs. 34 (34.0%)). The frequency distribution of biofilm-containing bacterial isolates is as follows; 36 (36.0%) *E. coli*, 22 (22.0%) *S. epidermidis*, 12 (12.0%) *S. aureus*, 16 (16.0%) *K. pneumoniae* and 14 (14.0%) *Proteus mirabilis* were detected. In addition, these results showed that most of the biofilm-producing bacteria were isolated from patients with urinary tract infections. Bacterial biofilm positivity was more common in older patients (30 years and above). The available results regarding gender determined that the patient group consisted of 40 (40.0%) males and 60 (60.0%) females. Since 60 (60.0%) of the patients with bacterial biofilm came from urban areas, the prevalence of bacterial biofilm was found to be higher in urban areas compared to rural areas.

الخلاصة

تُعدّ الأغشية الحيوية استراتيجية لبقاء البكتيريا.. إذ تنمو في بؤرة العدوى الأولية وتسمح للبكتيريا بالانتشار عبر مجرى الدم.. ويمكن للأغشية الحيوية أن تنشر البكتيريا العائمة وشظايا الأغشية الحيوية عبر الدم.. أجريت دراسة شملت 250 عينة يُشتبه بإصابتها بعدوى الأغشية الحيوية البكتيرية جُمعت من مستشفى الرفاعي العام، مدينة ذي قار، جنوب العراق، بين ديسمبر 2025 وأبريل 2026، من مرضى تتراوح أعمارهم بين 10 و45 عامًا. أظهرت النتائج الحالية أن 100 عينة (40.0%) كانت إيجابية، و150 عينة (60.0%) كانت سلبية لتكوين الأغشية الحيوية البكتيرية.. وتُشير هذه النتائج إلى أن انتشار الأغشية الحيوية البكتيرية أعلى في البكتيريا سالبة الغرام مقارنةً بالبكتيريا موجبة الغرام (66 (66.0%) مقابل 34 (34.0%)). وفيما يلي التوزيع التكراري للعزلات البكتيرية الحاوية على الأغشية الحيوية: تم الكشف عن 36 (36.0%) من بكتيريا الإشريكية القولونية، و22 (22.0%) من بكتيريا المكورات العنقودية البشرية، و12 (12.0%) من بكتيريا المكورات العنقودية الذهبية، و16 (16.0%) من بكتيريا الكلبسيلا الرئوية، و14 (14.0%) من بكتيريا المتقلبة. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، أظهرت هذه النتائج أن معظم البكتيريا المنتجة للغشاء الحيوي عُزلت من مرضى مصابين بعدوى المسالك البولية. وكان وجود الغشاء الحيوي البكتيري أكثر شيوعًا لدى المرضى الأكبر سنًا (30 عامًا فأكثر). وأظهرت النتائج المتاحة المتعلقة بالجنس أن مجموعة المرضى تتكون من 40 (40.0%) من الذكور و60 (60.0%) من الإناث. وبما أن 60 (60.0%) من المرضى المصابين بالغشاء الحيوي البكتيري كانوا من المناطق الحضرية، فقد وُجد أن انتشار الغشاء الحيوي البكتيري أعلى في المناطق الحضرية مقارنةً بالمناطق الريفية..

Keywords: Biofilm, Gram-negative bacteria, Gram-positive bacteria, Bacterial biofilm infection.

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Introduction

Bacteria have historically been studied as single-celled planktonic organisms, but outside the laboratory, most bacteria live in organized multicellular communities embedded in a matrix of extracellular polymers called biofilms (Flemming & Wuertz, 2019). Biofilms are a natural mode of bacterial growth in nature (Hernández-Jiménez et al., 2013).

Biofilm formation is one of the most effective factors in bacterial pathogenicity. Biofilm can cause bacteria to develop antimicrobial resistance and interfere with host defense mechanisms. It can also serve as a reservoir for these pathogens to replicate. Because microorganisms can adhere to surfaces, and some species form biofilms there, it is a risk factor for ventilator-associated pneumonia (Mazloomirad et al., 2021). Bacterial biofilms have become a significant contributor to global health problems due to antibiotic resistance, the host's immune defense system, and other external pressures. Biofilms have often been found on the surface of hospital instruments and body tissue, in industry, food processing units, and in natural environments (Schulze et al., 2021). The National Institutes of Health has suggested that 80% of all known human infections are associated with biofilms, and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention has reported that more than 65% of all hospital-acquired infections are attributable to biofilms. In 2004, biofilms were conceptually reported as an underlying cause of the nonhealing and prolonged infections observed in many, if not all, chronic wounds (Percival & Bowler, 2004). By 2008, James and colleagues confirmed this hypothesis, reporting that 60% of the chronic wounds they sampled contained biofilms. More recently, the role of biofilms in delayed healing and increased infection risk in chronic wounds has been further supported by both in vitro and in vivo studies (Fazli et al., 2011). In persistent infections, biofilms are rarely overcome by the host immune response and cause overproduction of polymorphonucleocytes and white blood cells, leading to chronic inflammation and delayed wound healing. This, in turn, leads to further complications in the tissue environment. A recent study by Akers and colleagues provided evidence that biofilms play an important role in skin and wound infections, emphasizing the polymicrobial nature of biofilms as a risk factor for recurrent skin and wound infections (Akers et al., 2014).

Bacterial biofilm investigations can be performed using various phenotypic methods. The Congo red agar test, developed by (Freeman et al., 1989), is based on subculture of bacterial strains onto brain heart infusion agar supplemented with sucrose and Congo red dye. Studies have shown that this method has low accuracy, but it is inexpensive and easy to implement, and evaluation criteria are based on visual analysis of the color of colonies grown on the agar. As demonstrated in the microtitration polystyrene test, the addition or substitution of certain substances or modification of certain parameters can increase the accuracy of this method (Kaiser et al., 2013).

The Aim of Study

This study provides a pioneering tool for identifying individuals more susceptible to biofilm-associated infections and for developing targeted therapies that enhance the immune response to biofilm. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that understanding anti-biofilm strategies can help disrupt biofilm structures and sensitize bacteria to antibiotics.

Materials and Methods

Our study, designed as a control case study and involving 250 samples, began in December 2025. Patients were interviewed face-to-face at Al-Rifai General Hospital in Thi-Qar Governorate, Southern Iraq, and each patient's clinical history, laboratory results, and physical examination findings were obtained. Each case was identified by asking about the patient's age, gender, signs and symptoms, as well as whether they had been administered antibiotics in the week prior to collection. Patients diagnosed with Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) were interviewed, and ear, throat, and wound swab samples were collected according to clinical and laboratory standards. Clinical criteria were determined based on clinical signs and symptoms. In addition to laboratory requirements, midstream urine samples were collected in sterile screw-cap containers to confirm urinary tract infections.

These samples were analyzed microscopically for the presence of pus cells, bacteria from the patient and control groups, and positive urine cultures containing at least 10⁵ CFU/ml of bacteria. Subsequently, all samples were cultured on Blood Agar, MacConkey Agar, and Mannitol Salt Agar using a sterile standard loop for 24 hours at 37°C. The morphology of cells in pure bacterial colonies was examined using Gram staining chemicals. All bacterial isolates were identified biochemically (manual and automated tests). PCR testing was performed on bacterial colonies to confirm all isolations using the 16S rRNA gene and resistance gene detection.

Polymerase Chain Reaction Primers

PCR primers for molecular detection of biofilm bacteria-based 16S ribosomal RNA gene were used in this study using the NCBI Genbank database and the Primer 3 program. These primers were also provided by Scientific Researcher.Co.Ltd, Iraq, in the following formats:

Table 1. PCR Primers with Nucleotide Sequences and Product Sizes

Primer	Sequence (5'-3')	Product Size	Genbank
16S rRNA gene Escherichia coli	F TCCCCATCTTTGTCCATCTC	453bp	LR739012.1
	R AGAATACCGGTGACGAATGC		
16S rRNA gene Staphylococcus aureus	F GAGGGTCATTGGAACTGGA	611bp	L37597.1
	R TAGCACGTGTGTAGCCCAA		
16S rRNA gene <i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	F CAGAAGAAGCACCGGCTAAC	368bp	LR739004.1
	R CGGTTTCAAGACCACAACCT		
16S rRNA gene Klebsiella pneumoniae	F ACCTTGGCGATTGACGTTAC	562bp	HG416956.1
	R AAGGCACCAATCCATCTCTG		
16S rRNA gene Staphylococcus epidermidis	F GAGCTTGCTCCTGACGTT	674bp	L37605.1
	R AGACCAGAAAGTCGCCTTCG		

Table2. Biofilm-Related Genes PCR Primers, Nucleotide Sequences and Product Sizes

Primer	Sequence (5'-3')	Product Size	Genbank
<i>fimH</i> Escherichia coli gene	F CTGGTCGGTAAATGCCTGGT	392bp	JF289169.1
	R AGCCAGCTTTAATCGCCACT		
<i>invention</i> Staphylococcus aureus gene	F AGCGAAGTCAGACACTTGCT	506bp	KT321150.1
	R GCGACTATCAATAAAGAGTGCGA		
<i>mrpA</i> gene <i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	F GTTGTGTGCGGGTCTGCTTT	438bp	NC_010554.1
	R TGGAACAGCAGCTTCAGATG		
<i>fimH</i> gene Klebsiella pneumoniae	F TCGTTAATCGCGGTGCTGAT	447bp	FJ483600.1
	R GATGATCGACTGCACGTTGC		
<i>IcaA</i> <i>Staphylococcus</i>	F AGCTAATGCACTCAATGAGGGA	423bp	KU595712.1
	R TCAGGCACTAACATCCAGCA		

Statistical Analysis

Data were collected, summarized, analyzed and presented using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26 and Microsoft Office Excel 2010. Numeric data were presented as mean, standard deviation after performance of Kolmogorov- Smirnov normality test and making decision about normally and non-normally distributed variables. Independent sample t-test was used to study difference in mean between any two groups provided that the variable is normally distributed. One way Anova test used to study difference in mean between more than two groups provided that the variable is normally distributed. Chi-square test was used to study association between any two categorical variables. Odds ratio and 95% confidence interval was estimated to measure risk. The level of significance was considered at P-value of less 0.05 and highly significant level at 0.01 or less (Daniel, 2009).

Results

Bacterial Isolation

A case-control study of 250 samples suspected of bacterial biofilm infection was collected from 10 to 45 years old patients (aged 10 to 45) at Al-Rifai Teaching Hospital, Thi-Qar Governorate, southern Iraq the present results show that 100 (40.0%) samples were positive for bacterial biofilm formation, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Percentage of Bacterial Biofilm Formation in Samples

Demographic Characteristics of Patients with Bacterial Biofilm Formation Infection and Healthy Control Individuals

Positive bacterial biofilm after isolation of samples containing bacterial biofilm, the demographic characteristics of patients and control subjects were investigated in this study and the results are shown in Table 3. The mean age of patients with bacterial biofilm positive was 28.24 ± 8.51 , and the mean age of the control group was 25.64 ± 6.17 , and no significant difference was found between the patients and the control group in terms of mean age ($P = 0.083$). Similarly, no significant difference was found in the species distribution by age in the patient and control groups ($P = 0.081$). On the other hand, the current results show that most of the patients with positive bacterial biofilm enrolled in this study were in the group over 30 years of age (Figure2).

In terms of gender, the patient group included 40 (40.0%) males and 60 (60.0%) females, while the control group included 54 (54.0%) males and 46 (46.0%) females (Figure 3). There was no significant difference in the species distribution of patient and control cases by gender ($P = 0.161$). According to the present results, most of the patients with positive bacterial biofilm included in this study were female. Regarding place of residence, the patient group consisted of 60 (60.0%) cases from urban areas and 40 (40.0%) cases from rural areas, while the control group consisted of 70 (70.0%) cases from urban areas and 30 (30.0%) cases from rural areas. There was no significant difference in the species distribution of patient and control cases by place of residence ($P = 0.295$). The above results ensured statistical matching between the patient group and the control group in terms of age, gender, and residence, which is a prerequisite for this type of case-control study.

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics of Patients with Bacterial Biofilm Formation Infection and Healthy Control Individuals

Characteristic	With patients biofilm bacteria <i>n</i> = 100	Healthy control <i>n</i> = 100	<i>P</i>
Age (years)			
Mean \pm SD	28.24 \pm 8.51	25.64 \pm 6.17	0.083
Range	10-45	16-42	† NS
< 20, <i>n</i> (%)	18 (18.0%)	14 (14.0%)	0.081
20-29, <i>n</i> (%)	34 (34.0%)	56 (56.0%)	¥
\geq 30, <i>n</i> (%)	48 (48.0%)	30 (30.0%)	NS
Gender			
Male, <i>n</i> (%)	40 (40.0%)	54 (54.0%)	0.161
Female, <i>n</i> (%)	60 (60.0%)	46 (46.0%)	¥ NS
Residence			
Urban, <i>n</i> (%)	60 (60.0%)	70 (70.0%)	0.295
Rural, <i>n</i> (%)	40 (40.0%)	30 (30.0%)	¥ NS

Note: *n*: number of cases; SD: standard deviation; †: independent samples t-test; ¥: Chi-square test; S: significant at $P > 0.05$; NS: not significant at $P > 0.05$

Figure 2. Distribution of Patients According to Age Groups

Figure 3. Distribution of Patients and Control Subject According to Gender

Distribution of Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Biofilm-Forming Infectious Bacteria Based on Gram Staining

The species distribution of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria according to Gram stain is shown in Figure 4. The present results show that 34 (34.0%) of the bacterial isolates were gram-positive bacteria and 66 (66.0%) were gram-negative bacteria.

Figure 4: Percentages of Biofilm-Forming Infectious Bacteria According to Gram Staining

Automation Identification

The VITEK-2 system was used for the automatic identification of ID-Gram-positive cocci (ID-GP cards) and ID-Gram-negative cocci (ID-GN cards) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The VITEK-2 ID-GP card identifies 124 species of staphylococci, streptococci, and enterococci, and a select group of Gram-positive organisms in 8 hours or less. The VITEK-2 ID-GN card identifies 154 species of Enterobacteriaceae and a select group of non-glucose-fermenting Gram-negative organisms in 10 hours. The VITEK-2 system results confirmed a probable (98-99%) positive result for bacterial species as a select organism. In the present study, the results were 36 (36.0%) *Escherichia coli*, 22 (22.0%) *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, 12 (12.0%) *Staphylococcus aureus*, and 16 (16.0%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. and 14 (14.0%) *Proteus mirabilis*.

Distribution of Bacterial Isolates among Clinical Samples

The species distribution of biofilm bacterial isolates among clinical samples is shown in Table2.

Table2. Distribution of Bacterial Isolates among Clinical Samples

Species	Sample type	Isolatenumber of	%
<i>E. coli</i>	UTI	22	22.0%
	Q-tips	4	4.0%
	Throat swab	6	6.0%
	Wound cleaning stick	4	4.0%
<i>S.epidermidis</i>	UTI	12	12.0%
	Wound cleaning stick	10	10.0%
<i>S. aureus</i>	UTI	6	6.0%
	Throat swab	2	2.0%
	Q-tips	2	2.0%

	Wound cleaning stick	2	2.0%
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	UTI	10	10.0%
	Q-tips	4	4.0%
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	UTI	4	4.0%
	Q-tips	6	6.0%
	Throat swab	6	6.0%

Molecular Diagnosis of Bacterial Isolation

The species distribution according to the PCR results performed for the detection of 16S rRNA genes of different bacterial species of patients with bacterial biofilm infection is shown in Figure 5. The current results show that the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *Escherichia coli* was reported in 36 (36.0%) patients in Figure 6; the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *S. epidermidis* was reported in 22 (22.0%) patients in Figure 8; the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *S. aureus* was reported in 12 (12.0%) patients in Figure 10; 16S ribosomal RNA gene 16 (16.0%) for detecting *K. pneumoniae* and 14 (14.0%) for *P. mirabilis* are shown in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11, Figure 12, Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15, respectively.

Figure 2. PCR Diagnosis Percentages of Bacterial Biofilm Formation Infection

Figure 6. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *Escherichia coli* isolates. M (Marker ladder 2000-100bp). Lanes (1-24) show positive *Escherichia coli* isolates with a product size of 453bp showing the 16S ribosomal RNA gene. NTC: negative control

Figure 7. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the virulence factor biofilm-associated (FimH) gene in *Escherichia coli* isolates. M (Marker ladder 2000-100bp). Lanes (1-24) show some positive *Escherichia coli* isolates with a product size of 392bp showing the FimH gene. NTC: negative control

Figure 8. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* isolates

Figure 9. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the virulence factor biofilm formation (*icaA*) gene in *Staphylococcus epidermidis* isolates

Figure 10. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates

Figure 11. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the virulence factor biofilm formation (*ica*) gene in *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates

Figure 12. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the detection of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates

Figure 13. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the virulence factor biofilm-associated (*FimH*) gene in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates

Figure 14. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene for the identification of *Proteus mirabilis* isolates

Figure 15. Agarose gel electrophoresis image showing PCR product analysis of the virulence factor biofilm formation (*mrpA*) gene in *Proteus mirabilis* isolates

Discussion

Biofilm formation begins with bacterial attachment, followed by proliferation and maturation, leading to increased resistance to antimicrobial agents. These biofilms act as barriers, making infections difficult to treat and contributing to their persistence (Khan et al., 2021). The current results show that 100% (40.0%) of the samples were positive for bacterial biofilm formation. This is similar to the results of (Agarwal et al., 2022), who reported that 40.0% of the samples were positive for bacterial biofilm formation. Several studies have shown that bacterial biofilm formation is significantly prevalent in Iraq. For example, a study of *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates obtained from different clinical sources in Baghdad revealed that 80% of the isolates tested exhibited strong biofilm production (Abdulhussein & Mahdi, 2023). Overall, the data indicate a high prevalence of bacterial biofilm formation in Iraq, with prevalence rates ranging from 50% to 100% among different bacterial species and clinical conditions. In particular, biofilm production has been shown to contribute to multidrug resistance in a significant proportion of isolates, posing a significant challenge in clinical settings. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring biofilm formation in clinical laboratories to guide appropriate antibiotic therapy and address the increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant bacteria (Gedefie et al., 2023).

Bacterial biofilms are common in elderly patients, especially in the context of infections such as urinary tract infections (UTIs) (Perry & Tan, 2023). The mean age of patients with positive bacterial biofilm was 28.24 ± 8.51 years, while the mean age of the control group was 25.64 ± 6.17 years. There was no significant difference in mean age between patients and the control group ($P = 0.083$). On the other hand, the current results show that most of the 48 (48.0%) patients with positive bacterial biofilm who participated in this study were in the over 30 year old group. The current results indicate that bacterial biofilm is more common in elderly patients, which is consistent with several studies showing that biofilms play an important role in various infections affecting elderly individuals (Yeo et al., 2018). Furthermore, a study of chronic geriatric patients with indwelling catheters found a high prevalence of Gram-negative microorganisms capable of producing biofilms, highlighting the need for new antimicrobial agents (Cangui-Panchi et al., 2022).

Bacterial biofilms show varying prevalence in urban and rural areas due to different environmental conditions. The current study shows that 60% (60.0%) of patients with bacterial biofilms came from urban areas. Therefore, the highest prevalence of bacterial biofilms in patients from urban areas may be due to the presence of hospital wastewater as a hotspot for the spread of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) and biofilm formation (Buelow et al., 2023). Our study is consistent with (Widyarman et al., 2021), who found that bacterial biofilm prevalence was higher in urban areas compared to rural areas. In urban settings, studies have shown that urbanization causes shifts in bacterial diversity and community composition, leading to higher bacterial diversity in urban areas compared to rural areas (Gao et al., 2023). Furthermore, urban Primary Health Care Centers (PHCs) were found to have higher bacterial airborne contamination compared to rural PHCs, with most sampling sites showing higher bacterial loads in urban environments (Monteiro et al., 2021). These findings suggest that urban areas harbor a higher prevalence of bacterial biofilms, potentially due to factors such as increased human activity, population density, and environmental conditions associated with urbanization.

Our study shows that the prevalence of bacterial biofilm is higher in gram-negative bacteria compared to gram-positive bacteria (66 (66.0%) vs. 34 (34.0%)). Gram-negative bacteria are known to form biofilms as a defense mechanism against antimicrobial agents and host immune responses, and thus, they persist and cause recurrent infections (Ruhail & Kataria, 2021). Gram-negative bacteria tend to form biofilms more frequently compared to gram-positive bacteria. This is largely due to the differences in their cell wall structures and compositions. Gram-negative bacteria have an outer membrane that provides additional protection and flexibility, which makes them more adept at forming biofilms in a variety of environments. Additionally, gram-negative bacteria generally possess adhesive structures such as pili and

fimbriae that aid biofilm formation (Pompilio et al., 2021). In contrast, gram-positive bacteria in catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) showed lower biofilm formation rates; 84.8% of gram-positive cocci and 89.2% of gram-negative bacilli form biofilm (Pokharel et al., 2022).

The results of our study showed that the species distribution of biofilm-producing bacterial isolates was as follows: *E. coli* in 36 (36.0%), *S. epidermidis* in 22 (22.0%), *S. aureus* in 12 (12.0%), *K. pneumoniae* in 16 (16.0%), and *Proteus mirabilis* in 14 (14.0%). Furthermore, the present results indicate that most biofilm-producing bacteria were isolated from patients with UTI. Bacterial biofilms are an important cause of UTI, accounting for approximately 65% of nosocomial infections and 80% of all microbial infections (Mancuso et al., 2024). A biofilm develops on the uroepithelium, and bacteria penetrate this biofilm, which protects them from mechanical urine flow, host defenses, and antibiotics, complicating bacterial elimination and becoming responsible for colonization and persistence (Sharma et al., 2023). Various bacterial species can form biofilms as a survival strategy, unlike other multidrug resistance mechanisms. This is particularly relevant for *E. coli*, which represents one of the most common causes of UTIs (Zhou et al., 2023). *E. coli* acts as an opportunistic or intrinsic pathogen, causing diseases such as meningitis, peritonitis, and septicemia, as well as intestinal, extraintestinal, urinary, and gastrointestinal infections (Denamur et al., 2021). For example, uropathogenic *E. coli* (UPEC) is the most common cause of urinary tract infections (UTIs) (Alvarez-Fraga et al., 2022). Previous studies have shown that biofilms help *E. coli* adhere to host cells, resist shear forces associated with urine flow, and contribute to bacterial persistence and chronic infection (Behzadi et al., 2020). Biofilm formation by *E. coli* contributes to the emergence of various infections and complicates their eradication. Factors such as different extracellular extensions that contribute to *E. coli* surface colonization and their precisely regulated expression and activity lead to mature biofilm formation (Alshaikh et al., 2024).

Infections are common and a significant cause of morbidity and mortality. Therefore, interventions to prevent bacterial infections are reasonable, and successful strategies, particularly those employing antibiotic prophylaxis, have been developed in recent years. However, antibiotic prophylaxis is not without its side effects, particularly the development of bacterial resistance, especially with long-term treatment. This is a serious problem not only in the general population but also worldwide, reducing the effectiveness of prophylactic antibiotics and increasing morbidity and mortality. Identifying risk factors for infection is crucial for developing comprehensive prevention strategies that limit antibiotic prophylaxis to high-risk groups to minimize bacterial resistance (Fernandez et al., 2016).

The species distribution of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria for bacterial biofilm formation was examined using the Gram stain method. The present results indicate that Gram-negative bacteria have a higher tendency to form biofilms than Gram-positive bacteria. Furthermore, the present results suggest that female gender is a risk factor associated with biofilm formation.

Conclusion

This study provides a pioneering tool for identifying individuals more susceptible to biofilm-associated infections and for developing targeted therapies that enhance the immune response to biofilm. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that understanding anti-biofilm strategies can help disrupt biofilm structures and sensitize bacteria to antibiotics. Understanding the interaction mechanisms between biofilm-forming bacteria and the receptor is crucial for developing new and more effective treatments for chronic diseases associated with bacterial infections.

References

- Abdulhussein, N., & Mahdi, M. (2023). Isolation and identification of multi-drug resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolated from clinical samples at Baghdad, Iraq. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science*, 15(2), 663–671. <https://doi.org/10.31018/jans.v15i2.4560>
- Agarwal, R., Gupta, E., Rathore, R. S., Ashopa, V., Gupta, E., & Prakash, P. (2022). To study drug resistance and biofilm production in Gram-negative isolates from clinical samples. *Indian Journal of Microbiology Research*, 9(3), 200–206. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijmr.2022.043>
- Akers, K. S., Mende, K., Cheatle, K. A., Zera, W. C., Yu, X., Beckius, M. L., Aggarwal, D., Li, P., Sanchez, C. J., Wenke, J. C., & Infectious Disease Clinical Research Program Trauma Infectious Disease Outcomes Study Group. (2014). Biofilms and persistent wound infections in United States military trauma patients: A case–control analysis. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 14, 190. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2334-14-190>
- Alshaikh, S. A., El-Banna, T., Sonbol, F., El-Mahallawy, H., El-Kholy, A., & Abdelrahman, Y. (2024). Correlation between antimicrobial resistance, biofilm formation, and virulence determinants in uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* from Egyptian hospital. *Annals of Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobials*, 23, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12941-024-00664-6>
- Alvarez-Fraga, L., Phan, M.-D., Goh, K. G. K., Forde, B. M., Chong, T. M., Yin, W.-F., Chan, K.-G., Schembri, M. A., & Beatson, S. A. (2022). Differential Afa/Dr fimbriae expression in the multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* ST131 clone. *mBio*, 13(1), e03519-21. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.03519-21>
- Behzadi, P., Urban, E., & Gajdács, M. (2020). Association between biofilm-production and antibiotic resistance in uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC): An in vitro study. *Diseases*, 8(2), 17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diseases8020017>
- Buelow, E., Dauga, C., Carrion, C., Mathé-Hubert, H., Bellanger, X., Eckert, C., Boudry, P., Gbaguidi-Haore, H., Bertrand, X., Grall, N., & others. (2023). Hospital and urban wastewaters shape the matrix and active resistome of environmental biofilms. *Water Research*, 244, 120408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120408>
- Cangui-Panchi, S. P., Ñacato-Toapanta, A. L., Enríquez-Martínez, L. J., Reyes, J., Garzon-Chavez, D., & Machado, A. (2022). Biofilm-forming microorganisms causing hospital-acquired infections from intravenous catheter: A systematic review. *Current Research in Microbial Sciences*, 3, 100175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmicr.2022.100175>
- Daniel, W. W. (2009). *Biostatistics: A foundation for analysis in the health sciences* (9th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Denamur, E., Clermont, O., Bonacorsi, S., & Gordon, D. (2021). The population genetics of pathogenic *Escherichia coli*. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 19(1), 37–54. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-020-0416-x>
- Fazli, M., Bjarnsholt, T., Kirketerp-Møller, K., Jørgensen, A., Andersen, C. B., Givskov, M., & Tolker-Nielsen, T. (2011). Quantitative analysis of the cellular inflammatory response against biofilm bacteria in chronic wounds. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, 19(3), 387–391. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1524-475X.2011.00681.x>
- Fernandez, J., Tandon, P., Mensa, J., & Garcia-Tsao, G. (2016). Antibiotic prophylaxis in cirrhosis: Good and bad. *Hepatology*, 63(6), 2019–2031. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.28230>
- Flemming, H.-C., & Wuertz, S. (2019). Bacteria and archaea on Earth and their abundance in biofilms. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 17(4), 247–260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-019-0158-9>
- Freeman, D. J., Falkiner, F. R., & Keane, C. T. (1989). New method for detecting slime production by coagulase negative staphylococci. *Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 42(8), 872–874. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jcp.42.8.872>

- Gao, D., Zhang, N., Liu, S., Li, Y., Wang, Y., Zhang, J., & Zhang, X. (2023). Urbanization imprint on soil bacterial communities in forests and grasslands. *Forests*, *14*(1), 38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14010038>
- Gedefie, A., Alemayehu, E., Mohammed, O., Bambo, G. M., Tarekegn, Z. S., Asmamaw, D., Teshome, D., & Molla, M. D. (2023). Prevalence of biofilm-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* clinical isolates: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE*, *18*(11), e0287211. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287211>
- Hernández-Jiménez, E., Del Campo, R., Toledano, V., Vallejo-Cremades, M. T., Muñoz, A., Largo, C., Arnalich, F., García-Río, F., Cubillos-Zapata, C., & López-Collazo, E. (2013). Biofilm vs. planktonic bacterial mode of growth: Which do human macrophages prefer? *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, *441*(4), 947–952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2013.11.012>
- Kaiser, T. D. L., Pereira, E. M., Dos Santos, K. R. N., Maciel, E. L. N., Schuenck, R. P., & Nunes, A. P. F. (2013). Modification of the Congo red agar method to detect biofilm production by *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease*, *75*(3), 235–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diagmicrobio.2012.11.014>
- Khan, J., Tarar, S. M., Gul, I., Nawaz, U., & Arshad, M. (2021). Challenges of antibiotic resistance biofilms and potential combating strategies: A review. *3 Biotech*, *11*(4), Article 169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-021-02707-x>
- Mancuso, G., Trinchera, M., Midiri, A., Zummo, S., Biondo, C., & Beninati, C. (2024). Novel antimicrobial approaches to combat bacterial biofilms associated with urinary tract infections. *Antibiotics*, *13*(2), 154. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics13020154>
- Mazloomirad, F., Hasanzadeh, S., Sharifi, A., Nikbakht, G., Roustaei, N., & Khoramrooz, S. S. (2021). Identification and detection of pathogenic bacteria from patients with hospital-acquired pneumonia in southwestern Iran; evaluation of biofilm production and molecular typing of bacterial isolates. *BMC Pulmonary Medicine*, *21*, Article 408. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-021-01773-3>
- Monteiro, A., Almeida, B., Paciência, I., Rufo, J., Silva, D., Moreira, A., Delgado, L., & Padrão, P. (2021). Bacterial contamination in health care centers: Differences between urban and rural settings. *Atmosphere*, *12*(4), 450. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12040450>
- Percival, S. L., & Bowler, P. G. (2004). Biofilms and their potential role in wound healing. *Wounds*, *16*(7), 234–240.
- Perry, E. K., & Tan, M. W. (2023). Bacterial biofilms in the human body: Prevalence and impacts on health and disease. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, *13*, 1237164. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2023.1237164>
- Pokharel, K., Dawadi, B. R., & Shrestha, L. B. (2022). Role of biofilm in bacterial infection and antimicrobial resistance. *JNMA: Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, *60*(253), 836–840. <https://doi.org/10.31729/jnma.7785>
- Pompilio, A., Scribano, D., Sarshar, M., Di Bonaventura, G., Palamara, A. T., & Ambrosi, C. (2021). Gram-negative bacteria holding together in a biofilm: The *Acinetobacter baumannii* way. *Microorganisms*, *9*(7), 1353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9071353>
- Ruhal, R., & Kataria, R. (2021). Biofilm patterns in Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. *Microbiological Research*, *251*, 126829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2021.126829>
- Schulze, A., Mitterer, F., Pombo, J. P., & Schild, S. (2021). Biofilms by bacterial human pathogens: Clinical relevance—Development, composition and regulation—Therapeutical strategies. *Microbial Cell*, *8*(2), 28–56. <https://doi.org/10.15698/mic2021.02.741>

- Sharma, S., Mohler, J., Mahajan, S. D., Schwartz, S. A., Bruggemann, L., & Aalinkeel, R. (2023). Microbial biofilm: A review on formation, infection, antibiotic resistance, control measures, and innovative treatment. *Microorganisms*, 11(6), 1614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11061614>
- Widyarman, A. S., Theodorea, C. F., Udawatte, N. S., Drestia, A. M., Bachtiar, E. W., Bachtiar, B. M., & Irawan, B. (2021). Diversity of oral microbiome of women from urban and rural areas of Indonesia: A pilot study. *Frontiers in Oral Health*, 2, 738306. <https://doi.org/10.3389/froh.2021.738306>
- Yeo, H. J., Yoon, S. H., Lee, S. E., Cho, W. H., Kim, D., Kim, Y. S., Kim, H. S., Lee, J. H., & Kim, Y. J. (2018). Bacterial biofilms on extracorporeal membrane oxygenation catheters. *ASAIO Journal*, 64(4), e48–e54. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MAT.0000000000000662>
- Zhou, Y., Zhou, Z., Zheng, L., Gong, Z., Wang, Y., Li, Y., & Zhang, X. (2023). Urinary tract infections caused by uropathogenic *Escherichia coli*: Mechanisms of infection and treatment options. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(13), 10537. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241310537>

